

APPLICATION OF PROJECT TECHNOLOGY ON THE ENGLISH LESSONS

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ABSTRACT

The article considers the project method on the English lessons which can assist the decision of problems at a new level of learning foreign language and the developing of the creative person.

The modern student is a creative and active person. He seeks to express himself in work and show the result of this work. The modern teaching methodology requires a student-centered approach and the development of the communicative competence of students, and therefore in the process of work we put in the center of our attention the student, his inner world, his interests, his development. This approach to teaching changes the relationship between student and teacher.

In our opinion, the use of the method of project activity of students in the classroom, which helps the general development of the personality of students, develops their inner world, outlook, and creative activity, contributes to the teaching of the English language. In a foreign school, the project method has been used since the late 80s of the XX century. In our country, this method began to be actively used in the late 90s of the last century, and is now becoming more widespread. Completing the assignments, students get acquainted with the peculiarities

of the culture of the language being studied and thereby realize another goal of learning a foreign language - the formation of regional competence. The project method plays an important role in teaching English, allows solving problems at a new stage of its study and contributes to the creative development of the individual. A distinctive feature of the project is the active use of the means of the foreign language being studied. In the process of completing the assigned tasks, students get acquainted with the texts and perform tasks in a foreign language, while simultaneously repeating the lexical and grammatical material already passed. Schoolchildren themselves find the missing information, which contains regional geographic, lexical, grammatical material, using for this not only the material of the textbook, but also other sources of information. The final product is presented in a foreign language. The project method reflects a differentiated approach to teaching, which allows students to independently acquire knowledge in the process of solving practical problems that require the integration of

knowledge from various fields. This method contributes to the achievement of the didactic goal through the detailed elaboration of the problem. This technique requires active, independent thinking of the child, which teaches not only to memorize and reproduce the knowledge that school gives them, but also to apply it in practice. Working on a project requires the ability to ask a problem, outline ways to solve it, plan the work and find the necessary material. In the process of this work, the student develops his intellectual abilities, as well as such character traits as perseverance, dedication, hard work and personal creativity. The goal of the project is to stimulate the interest of students in certain problems, involving the possession of the necessary amount of knowledge and, through project activities, providing for the solution of these problems, the ability to practically apply the knowledge gained, the development of critical thinking. The project method allows you to creatively apply language material and turn foreign language lessons into a discussion, research laboratory in which interesting, practically significant and accessible problems for students are solved, taking into account the peculiarities of the country's culture and, if possible, on the basis of intercultural interaction. By completing project assignments, schoolchildren acquire certain creative, intellectual and communication skills. This is manifested in the ability to work with information, analyze it, draw conclusions, generalizations. In this situation, the teacher is

assigned the role of a coordinator, source of information and an expert. The work should end with a practical result, designed in one way or another. To do this, it is necessary to teach children to think independently and solve assigned tasks. This can be helped by a creative atmosphere when studying the proposed research topic. When teaching a foreign language, the project method can be used in close connection with the curriculum. The assignments correspond to the individual level at which each student is. The teacher advises the student where to find information, how to write it down and how to present it. In this case, the student's fear of language disappears, as it happens in a regular lesson. The work makes it possible to apply the passed grammatical phenomena and structures. The main characteristic of this stage is the broadening of horizons, the intensification of search activity, the personal creativity of students. The positive side of this technology is that it is based on the independent work of schoolchildren at school and at home, encouraging them to search for new information from any source. The use of modern technical means helps to prepare the project more efficiently and in an interesting way.

Modern information technologies help to increase the motivation for learning a foreign language and improve the knowledge and culture of students and, under certain conditions, can be used in the educational process.

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